

Attitude of working women about female domestic violence in Ghotki district, Sindh

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ABSTRACT: The present study was conducted to evaluate the attitudes of working women about domestic violence in Ghotki District. The sample composed of 100 respondents (ie 50 married working women and 50 unmarried working women). This research findings conformed assumption and proved that the married and unmarried working women's attitudes about domestic violence is similar, there is no difference among their attitudes and both are realized women's right and conditions and the issue of domestic violence. Women are victimized in forms of Physical, Psychological and sexually by their parents, husbands, in-laws and also by their brothers at their homes. Present research concluded that working and nonworking women of Ghotki District have similar attitudes about domestic violence. In Pakistan there are some factors which are associated in domestic violence such as male dominant social structure, lack of education, falsified beliefs, imbalanced empowerment issues between males and females, lack of support from the government, low-economical status of women, and lack of awareness about women's rights. Therefore, the aim of this study is to understand the voices of stakeholders to reduce violence against women and to explore the possible community-based strategies that could be implemented in Pakistan. The research showed that all those factors reported in the previous literature are still present in the society and still need to be addressed to make progress towards the 2030 agenda of Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: Working Women, Problems, Abuse, Violence; Risk Factors

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1. Introduction

Domestic violence is a global socio-cultural concern faced by a majority of women. Domestic violence has a negative impact on women's social, physical, and psychological wellbeing. Domestic Violence against women is a sensitive socio-cultural issue and leading cause of concern world wide domestic Violence is classified as violent behaviour committed by family members, especially by a partner. Women face Domestic Violence regardless of their educational level, gender, and age. Domestic violence against women is generally viewed as a result of gender inequality and unequal balance of power. Men who perpetrate violence against their partners generally. Gender inequality is a global concern which is widely observed in many Asian cultures (Salima Muhammad-Farooq, 2017)

Since ancient time's women are considered as a property of men and this authority of men allow them to use Violence against women. In different parts of the world different factors are responsible for the variable status of women Violence against women is perhaps

the most shameful human rights violation, and it is perhaps the most pervasive. It knows no boundaries of geography, culture or wealth. As long as it continues, we cannot claim to be making real progress towards equality, development and peace. Violence against women is an international issue that is affecting the lives of women globally. Sustainable Development Goals also emphasizes gender equality and women's empowerment for peace around the world and each country is responsible to check within a country accordingly. In Pakistan women are vulnerable to violence because of the patriarchal society in the country; the resulting male dominance results in extensive violence against women. (ErajKhurram, 2009)

According to the 2017-2018 Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey, 28 percent of women aged 15 to 49 had experienced intimate partner violence in their lifetimes. This is a slight decrease from 32 percent of the women reported to have experienced physical violence at the hands of their partners in the 2012-2013 survey. But given that domestic violence is an issue shrouded in secrecy and shame, both sets of figures is likely a gross under-estimation. One suspects that it feels like there is a surge in violence because cases are getting more attention. Mainstream media is more attuned to the issue, and it is also being highlighted and discussed on social media platforms. These conversations have created heightened awareness among young women in particular, who are becoming increasingly vocal about their rights. The vast majority of these women belong to the educated, urban middle and upper classes. This is just the latest in the long history of the struggle against gender-based violence in Pakistan. (Dr NidaKirmani, 2021)

Nearly half of the women experience violence across their lifespan in all the provinces of Pakistan at an alarming rate. Despite knowing the prevalence, there has been meagre progress in developing strategies to combat violence at individual, family, or community level. Many interventions suggested in other countries have been pilot tested but the effects of those interventions had been limited. Therefore, the aim of this study is to understand the voices of stakeholders to reduce Violence against Women and to explore the possible community-based strategies that could be implemented in Pakistan. (TazeenSaeed Ali, 2020)

The year 2023 has not painted a hopeful picture. In just the first four months, an alarming 771 cases of violence against women were reported to the police. The Sustainable Social Development Organization (SSDO), which disclosed these figures, speculates that the actual numbers might be higher due to social stigmas surrounding reporting such incidents. The types of violence reported are distressing – with a staggering 529 cases of women being kidnapped, 119 cases of domestic violence, 56 cases of rape, and 37 cases of honor killing. These statistics are not just numbers; they represent the lives of women who have been violated, their basic human rights trampled upon. The National Report on the Status of Women in Pakistan 2023 further underscores the overarching gender inequality and the dire need for women empowerment. The report provides a snapshot of the situation of women on key themes related to Gender Equality and Women Empowerment, showcasing the paramount need for systemic change. (FerozSadruddin, 2023)

2. Literature Review

In South Asian societies, intimate partner violence (IPV) is one of the most common forms of family violence that includes physical, sexual, and emotional abuse and controlling behaviors by an intimate partner. IPV occurs in almost all settings, all socioeconomic, religious, and cultural groups. Although women can equally be violent in relationships with men, and violence also occurs in the same-sex partnerships, in many countries, the most common perpetrators of violence against women are male intimate partners. The problem is

so common and widespread that it has almost become an invisible form of crime and an everyday story in many households. (Elizabeth Croot, 2015)

The last few months have been particularly harrowing for Pakistani women. From the horrific case of 27-year-old Noor Muqaddam, who was brutally tortured and beheaded in the nation's capital on July 21, to that of Ayesha Ikram, a TikTok creator, who was harassed and groped on the country's Independence Day by more than 400 men on the grounds of one of the country's major national monuments, the Minar-e-Pakistan in Lahore – it feels as if violence against women has reached epidemic proportions. One such case was that of 28-year-old Samia Sarwar, whose murder was arranged by her family in 1999. She had been seeking a divorce from her violent husband, a decision her family did not support because it would have “dishonoured” the family name. She was shot dead in the offices of Hina Jilani, a well-respected Supreme Court lawyer and human rights activist. Sarwar had been there for a pre-arranged meeting with her mother to receive the divorce papers. Her murder started a national conversation about honour killings. Women's rights activists, including Jilani and her sister Asma Jahangir, also a renowned human rights lawyer and activist, highlighted it to advocate for an end to gender-based violence. But there were counter-protests from religious conservatives arguing that Sarwar's feminist lawyers had no business interfering in a question of “family honour”. To this day, the perpetrators have not been brought to justice. Another well-documented case is that of Mukhtaran Mai, who was gang-raped in June 2002 by four men in Meerwala village in southern Punjab's Muzaffargarh district. Mai was raped on the orders of a village council as “punishment” for her younger brother's alleged illegitimate relationship with a woman from a rival tribe. (Dr Nida Kirmani, 2021)

However, there were differences in the pattern of responses made by male and female participants. Most of the men did not consider keeping their wives short of money, forcing them to act against their will, depriving them of property rights, or limiting their access to education and medical assistance as abusive acts. These acts were considered as violent by female participants. Female participants, interestingly, did not consider insulting remarks, criticism, and isolation to be as serious forms of psychological abuse (Kamal, 2012).

More specifically, the most recent Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP) annual report (2015) cites that in the last three years alone, around 2,300 women have been victims of ‘honor’ killing. Other sources indicate that on average there are more than 10,000 ‘honor’ killings per year in just this one nation alone. It is estimated that Pakistan has the highest global rate of ‘honor’ killing (HRCP, 2015).

Background of Ghotki District Sindh, Pakistan

Ghotki (Urdu: گھوٹکی; Sindhi: گھوٽڪي) is a city in northern Sindh, Pakistan, and the headquarter of Ghotki District. Its population as of 2020 is 110,000. Ghotki is famous for its date palms. According to Mirza Kalich Beg, Ghotki was found by Pir Mohsin Shah during 1447 and had also constructed a glorious mosque. He has written that the previous name of Ghotki was لوبے صاحبان.

Law and order situation: The district of Ghotki is facing a serious law and order issue with numerous incidents of daily kidnappings, murders, and robberies. The challenging aspect of the problem is that these incidents are occurring in remote “Kacha areas” with difficult-to-access routes. The cabinet approved the proposal for the procurement of military-grade weapons and surveillance systems worth Rs2.79 billion to combat kidnapping and attacks on police forces in the reverie areas of Ghotki, Shikarpur, and Sukkur districts. The Home department was directed to seek an NOC from the Ministry of Interior for the purchase. The Sindh police planned to procure drone technology to use the unmanned aerial vehicles not only for surveillance but also for targeting bandits in reverie areas of the province. Outlaws found safe havens in the difficult terrain of four hard-

to-reach districts - Ghotki, Sukkur, Shikarpur, and Kashmore. Drones were previously used by the army during Zarb-i-Azab, but now law enforcement agencies use them extensively in counter-terrorism and to combat urban terrorism. This marks a major shift in operational techniques used by law enforcement agencies, including the Counter-Terrorism Department. Ghotki District (Sindhi: ضلعو گھوٽڪي; Urdu: ضلع گھوٽڪي) is a district of the province of Sindh, Pakistan, with headquarter the city of MirpurMathelo. Prior to its establishment as a district in 1993, it formed part of Sukkur District. Geography Ghotki District is stretched in 6975 km² (1,555,528 acres). 25,000 acres area of the district consisting of desert land, 402,578 acres (25.88%) is flooded (Katcha) area and remaining area lying between desert and flooded areas of district is cultivated. Desert area having wind-blown hills as AchroThar (White Desert). Flooded area (Kacha) is stretched on 87 km along Indus River from north - east to south - west of the district where forests exist in this area.

At the time of the 2017 census, Ghotki district had a population of 1,648,708, of which 360,821 (21.89%) lived in urban areas. Ghotki had a sex ratio of 939 females per 1000 males and a literacy rate of 40.88%: 57.46% for males and 23.35% for female. At the time of the 2017 census, 93.37% of the population spoke Sindhi, 2.49% Urdu, 1.64% Punjabi and 1.05% Saraiki as their first language.

Economy: Ghotki District has recently embraced sugar cane. The total acreage of cultivable land is 286,090 ha in 2019–20. The area under cultivation of sugar cane increased to 58,774 ha in 2019-20 from 6,511 ha in 2011–12. Five functional sugar mills are located in the district

Culture: Ghotki District is the land of Saint where is many Saint's Tomb. 1- Syed Anwar shah at Jahnpur 2- Syed Jaleel Shah Mast 5 kilometres away from MipurMathelo town 3- Nare shah Jelani In Ghotki Town. Ghotki District has many historical places, one of them is MatheloMoomalJi Mari, there is a museum and at the same place very popular saint Syed Nathan shah's (Naharo) Tomb.

Objectives

The Objective of the study is to find out the main factors which are responsible for the Violence against women in Ghotki District.

Specific Objectives

- To explore the social and economic problems of working women about domestic violence in Ghotki District. Sindh, Province
- To identify its underlying causes, consequently, this study aims to empirically examine the factors associated with women's attitudes toward violence in Ghotki District. Sindh. Province
- To explore perceptions regarding contributing factors to domestic violence among working women in Ghotki District. Sindh, Province
- To understand the voices of stakeholders to reduce Violence against Women and to explore the possible community-based strategies that could be implemented in Pakistan.

3. Research Methodology

The present study was conducted to evaluate the attitudes of working women about domestic violence in Ghotki District. The sample composed of 100 respondents (ie 50 married working women and 50 unmarried working women). The study was started in March, 2024. The sample composed of 100 respondents (ie 50 married working women and 50 unmarried working women) living in Ghotki district Sindh, and all women were selected for the study purpose. Primary data was taken from selected working women

For this purpose; interviews were conducted to collect the information, which was quantitative and qualitative in its nature. Given the nature of information required, the study was structured using qualitative and quantitative research methods. Qualitative and quantitative survey was conducted on social, economic conditions of working women Ghotki district Sindh, The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey method. Qualitative data collection was carried out using a comprehensive guideline questionnaire. In addition to individual interviews from each women and girls living in Ghotki district Sindh, This study endeavored to develop a fuller understanding of the domestic violence Ghotki district Sindh, in our society and their problems. The data collection working women living in Ghotki district Sindh, started the detailed interviews on the semi structured questionnaires were conducted from the 100 working Women living in Ghotki district Sindh, The interview was conducted at the home. The normal duration of the interview was about 30 minutes. Questions were asked by the researcher in their regional language and the relevant responses were recorded in the schedule. The researcher followed the free conversational style to elicit relevant information. As majority of working Women living in Ghotki district Sindh,. A rapport was first established with the respondents with the help of sharing some personal experience and confidence building measures. It was noticed that most respondents were free in sharing their experiences.

Locale

The data was collected from the Ghotki district Sindh, and the reason of choosing that area because this is the district of Ghotki is facing a serious law and order issue with numerous incidents of daily kidnappings, murders, and robberies, violence against women. Furthermore, this research highlights the need for awareness rising for women living in Ghotki district Sindh,

Procedure of Data Collection

Researcher started the data collection procedure by identifying the first participant, and then information was collected from the study was started in March, 2024. The sample composed of 100 respondents (ie 50 married working women and 50 unmarried working women) living in Ghotki district Sindh, on structured self-administered questionnaire., the research started with overall household survey in order to ascertain the number of the target population. Furthermore, this research highlights the need for awareness rising for working women about domestic violence living Ghotki district Sindh, after identifying the participants researcher acquired the consent of participant on consent paper and discussed the confidentiality of their responses.

Further interviews were scheduled by looking on the time and place as per the convenience of the participants. During the in-depth interview, the researcher made the place more private, and all interviews were conducted in a separate room. During the in-depth interview, the interviewer asked some initial questions and allowed the participants to speak whatever she wanted and was willing to share, meanwhile the researcher used interview guide for interactive and probing techniques to gather more data and deeper and concrete understandings of the responses. All the responses were recorded by using the gadget and recording technique, a diary was also maintained by the researcher for noting some important notes, points, or behaviours of the respondent i.e. facial expressions and body language. 94.1%

Ethical Consideration

The major ethical issues in conducting research will be identified in literature and persist throughout all phases of this research such as; deception and informed consent, respect for anonymity and confidentiality and respect of privacy & data storage. (Mauthner et al., 2005) It is important for the researcher to ensure a duty of care to participants that the

research is conducted in a safe and ethical manner (Sanjari 2014). The ethics of this research were preserved by not asking the names of the respondents. An informed consent letter was read to the respondents before filling out the questionnaire and if they were willing to participate in the study, they were asked to sign the consent letter (thumb impression if illiterate). The participation in this research was voluntary and at any point the respondent had the choice to withdraw their consent from participating in this study. No rewards were offered to the respondents for participation in the survey. The population of this research was working women living in Ghotki district Sindh. The selection criteria for target population were working women living in Ghotki district Sindh, The age of the respondent was above 22. A total of 100 working women living in Ghotki district Sindh, were sampled. Confidentiality will be maintained. This study is anonymous. We will not be collecting or retaining any information about your identity. Your identity will not be revealed in any publication resulting from this study (Bryman and Bell, 2007)

Background Information of working married and unmarried women living in Ghotki district, Sindh

Table No: 1 Detail Survey of female living in Ghotki district Sindh, Sample size: 150

S. No	Age	Education	Profession	Views of Working Married Women about domestic violence	Views of Working UN Married Women About domestic violence	Violence from Parents/Brothers	Violence from In-laws/Husband
20	22-35	Matriculation to F.A	Nurse, Peon, House worker	20 Married Women views the ingrained societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence, often normalized or brushed under the carpet. This cycle continues to sustain a culture of violence, fear, and silence.	10UN Married Women views that without community stakeholder's involvement and participation it could never be reduced Violence against women.	10 UN Married Women face violence from brothers	20 Married Women face violence from husband
30	25-45	F.A to B.A	Teachers, Clerks, House Worker	19 married women views the poverty, and lack of education create fertile grounds for a fundamental perpetration of violence on the female population	20 UN married women views the societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence on the female population	20 UN married women views that we face violence from parents	19 married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband
30		F.A to B.A	Teachers, Clerks, NGO Worker, House Worker	30married women views the violence against women appears to be at a peak and regressive forces are as vocal as ever, there are positive signs that young and educated, women, are becoming more aware and vocal in their resistance.	12 UN married women views the patriarchal norms, insufficient legal frameworks as primary contributors. Of violence on the female population	12 UN married women views that we face violence from parents	30 married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband
20		M.A.,MSc, M..B.A, M.B.B.S, M.Com	Teacher, Librarian Doctors, officers, Principles	31married women views that Domestic violence is not just about punishment and law enforcement; it's about altering deeply entrenched societal attitudes.	08 UN married women views the lack of education, awareness, and lack of women empowerment. These are main factors women face domestic violence.	08 UN married women views that we face violence from parents	31 married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband

Data Analysis and Results

Table No: 02 Views of working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh,

Views of working Married women about domestic violence	Views of working UN Married Women About domestic violence	No of working Married women about domestic violence	No of UN Married working Women about domestic violence	Percentage% UN Married working Women about domestic violence	Percentage% Married women about domestic violence
Ingrained societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence	Without community stakeholder's involvement and participation it could never be reduced Violence against women	20	10	20 %	20%
Poverty, and lack of education create fertile grounds for a fundamental furthering the perpetration of violence on the female population	Societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence on the female population	19	20	40%	19%
Violence against women appears to be at a peak and regressive forces are as vocal as ever, there are positive signs that young and educated, women, are becoming more aware and vocal in their resistance.	The Insufficient legal frame works as primary contributors. Of violence on the female population	30	12	24%	12%
Domestic violence is not just about punishment and law enforcement; it's about altering deeply entrenched societal attitudes.	Lack of education, awareness and lack of women empowerment. These are main factors women face domestic violence.	31	08	16%	8%
		Total .100	Total .50	100%	100%

Table No: 02 Views of w working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh, Percentage% UN Married working Women about domestic violence

The table 2 show's Views of working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh, and figure 1 describe the findings about the Views of w working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh, 20% married working women's views are societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence, 20 % Views of working UN Married women about domestic violence they told researcher without community stakeholder's involvement and participation it could never be reduced Violence against women, 19%working married women told researcher the Poverty and lack of education create fertile grounds for a fundamental furthering the perpetration of violence on the female population, 40% working UN Married women views was that the norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence on the female population, 12% Working married women told researcher the Violence against women appears to be at a peak and regressive forces are as vocal as ever, there are positive signs that young and educated, women, are becoming more aware and vocal in their resistance., 24% working UN Married women views was that the Insufficient legal frame works as primary contributors. Of violence on the female population, 8% Married working women views was that Domestic violence is not just about punishment and law enforcement; it's about altering deeply entrenched societal attitudes, 16% working UN Married women views was that the Lack of education, awareness and lack of women empowerment. These are main factors women face domestic violence. Views of w working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence Ghotki District Sindh,

Table No: 03 Views of Working Married and UN Married Women about domestic violence from parents and in- laws living in Ghotki District Sindh,

Violence from Parents/Brothers	Violence from In-laws/Husband	No of Married Women	No of UN Married Women	Percentage% UN Married working Women about domestic violence	Percentage% Married working Women about domestic violence
UN Married Women face violence from brothers	Married Women face violence from husband	20	10	20%	20%
UN married women views that we face violence from parents	Married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband	19	20	40%	19%
UN married women views that we face violence from parents.	Married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband	30	12	24%	20%
UN married women views that we face violence from brothers.	Married women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband	31	08	16%	31%
		Total: 1.00	Total: 50	100%	Total: 100%

The table 3 Views of Working Married and UN Married Women about domestic violence from parents and in-laws living in Ghotki District Sindh, and figure describe the 20% Married working Women face violence from husband, 20% UN Married working Women face violence from brothers, 19% Married working women views that we face violence from In-laws and Husband, 40% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from parents, 20% Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from In-laws/Husband, 24% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from parents, 31% Married working women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband and 16% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from brothers. Views of w working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh,

4. Major Findings

The findings of the study reveal that the views of working married and UN married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh, These finding shows the views of working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh, 20% married working women's views are societal norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence, 20 % views of working UN married women about domestic violence they told researcher without community stakeholder's involvement and participation it could never be reduced violence against women, 19% working married women told researcher the Poverty and lack of education create fertile grounds for a fundamental furthering the perpetration of violence on the female population, 40% working UN Married women views was that the norms and attitudes contribute to a destructive cycle of violence on the female population, 12% Working married women told researcher the Violence against women appears to be at a peak and regressive forces are as vocal as ever, there are positive signs that young and educated, women, are becoming more aware and vocal in their resistance, 24% working UN married women views was that the Insufficient legal frame works as primary contributors of violence on the female population, 8% Married working women views was that Domestic violence is not just about punishment and law enforcement; it's about altering deeply entrenched societal attitudes, 16% working UN Married women views was that the Lack of education, awareness and lack of women empowerment. These are main factors women face domestic violence. Views of working Married and UN Married women about domestic violence Ghotki District Sindh, The table 3 Views of Working Married and UN Married Women about domestic violence from parents and in-laws living in Ghotki District Sindh, and figure describe the 20% Married working Women face violence from husband, 20% UN Married working Women face violence from brothers, 19% Married working women views that we face violence from In-laws and Husband, 40% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from parents, 20% Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from In-laws/Husband, 24% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from parents, 31% Married working women views that we face violence from In-laws/Husband and 16% UN Married working Women told researcher that we face violence from brothers. Women are victimized in forms of Physical, Psychological and sexually by their parents, husbands, in-laws and also by their brothers at their homes. This paper aims to highlight the views of married, unmarried working women causes of domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh.

5. Suggestion and Recommendation

On the basis of the findings on various problems and issues following activities and programs are suggested to resolves the issues of female domestic violence in Ghotki District Sindh.

- To provide female education, awareness of law about domestic violence
- To Increase awareness about their rights and Pakistani laws to the women and Girls living Ghotki District Sindh.
- To improvements in the legal and social system are suggested.
- To give equal opportunity for women in their life decisions and they must have parental and in-laws support for their better life

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